

Nonstationary Data Stream Classification with Online Active Learning and Siamese Neural Networks ^{*}

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Abstract

We have witnessed in recent years an ever-growing volume of information becoming available in a streaming manner in various application areas. As a result, there is an emerging need for online learning methods that train predictive models on-the-fly. A series of open challenges, however, hinder their deployment in practice. These are, learning as data arrive in real-time one-by-one, learning from data with limited ground truth information, learning from nonstationary data, and learning from severely imbalanced data, while occupying a limited amount of memory for data storage. We propose the ActiSiamese algorithm, which addresses these challenges by combining online active learning, siamese networks, and a multi-queue memory. It develops a new density-based active learning strategy which considers similarity in the latent (rather than the input) space. We conduct an extensive study that compares the role of different active learning budgets and strategies, the performance with/without memory, the performance with/without ensembling, in both synthetic and real-world datasets, under different data nonstationarity characteristics and class imbalance levels. ActiSiamese outperforms baseline and state-of-the-art algorithms, and is effec-

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tive under severe imbalance, even only when a fraction of the arriving instances' labels is available. We publicly release our code to the community.

Keywords: incremental learning, active learning, data streams, concept drift, class imbalance

1. Introduction

There is at present an emerging need for online learning algorithms that train predictive models on-the-fly as new information is continually becoming available in a diverse set of applications, such as, monitoring systems (e.g. fault
5 detection in critical infrastructure systems [1], environmental monitoring [2]), security (e.g., spam filtering [3]), finance (e.g., credit card fraud detection [4]), and recommender systems [2]. Despite the great potential impact of online predictive models, there are some key open challenges and problems that affect their deployability in practical applications:

10 **Limited labelled data.** Acquiring ground truth information (e.g., labels in classification tasks) as instances arrive one-by-one can be costly or impossible in some real-time applications, such as, fault detection in critical infrastructures.

Nonstationary data. It refers to the problem of having a data distribution that is unknown, and it evolves over time [2]. For example, nonstationarity can
15 be caused by hardware faults (e.g., sensors in monitoring systems), changes in users' behaviour (e.g., to evade detection in security systems), seasonality or periodicity effects (e.g., consumption in a water distribution network), or changes in users' interests (e.g., in recommender systems).

Imbalanced data. Class imbalance refers to the problem of having a skewed
20 distribution of data [5]. It renders a learning algorithm ineffective in identifying minority class examples as its performance declines significantly. The problem becomes considerably harder for unlabelled and nonstationary data [3].

Therefore, for certain applications it is desirable to design an online learning algorithm with these properties: (i) be able to respond in real-time as instances
25 arrive one-by-one; (ii) be able to learn from limited labelled data, since in some

applications it is not possible to rely solely on supervision; (iii) be able to adapt, as an algorithm without these capabilities would be ineffective under nonstationary conditions; and (iv) perform well under severe imbalance. Importantly, finding a good trade-off between these requirements is a challenging task.

30 An effective way to deal with limited labelled data is the active learning paradigm, in which the classifier queries a human expert for the labels of selected instances [6]. A number of industry-scale applications have been realised using active learning, e.g., Google’s method for labelling malicious advertisements [7], and NVIDIA’s [8] and Tesla’s [9] methods for their autonomous vehicles with
35 self-driving capability. This paper focuses on *online active* learning. The key contributions of this work are the following:

1. We propose the ActiSiamese algorithm, which synergistically combines online active learning, siamese networks, and a multi-queue memory. While the majority of existing work focuses on uncertainty-based strategies, ActiSiamese proposes a new density-based strategy which considers similarity
40 in the encoding (rather than the input) space. ActiSiamese aims to address the key challenges of online learning that were previously discussed.
2. We conduct an extensive study that compares and examines the role of different active learning budgets and strategies (uncertainty-based, density-based), different neural network types (standard fully-connected, siamese),
45 the performance with and without memory, the performance with and without ensembling, in both synthetic and real-world datasets, under different nonstationarity characteristics and imbalance severity levels. ActiSiamese outperforms strong baselines and state-of-the-art algorithms, and is effective under conditions of extreme imbalance, even when only a
50 fraction of the arriving instances’ labels is available.
3. We provide new insights into learning from nonstationary and imbalanced data streams, which constitutes a challenging and largely unexplored area even in the presence of supervision [2, 3, 10].

55 ActiSiamese was first introduced in our brief conference paper [11], and this work constitutes a significant extension of that. Unlike our preliminary paper: (i) We extend ActiSiamese to allow ensembling to better address nonstationarity; (ii) We examine the performance of ActiSiamese in real-world datasets, as well as in more synthetic datasets; (iii) We perform an extensive empirical 60 analysis of ActiSiamese that examines the role of its various parameters; (iv) We perform an extensive comparative study as described above; and (iv) related work has been considerably enriched. We publicly release our code¹.

The paper is organised as follows. Preliminary material necessary to understand the contributions made is provided in Section 2. Related work is presented 65 in Section 3. ActiSiamese is described in Section 4. Our experimental setup is described in Section 5. An empirical analysis of ActiSiamese is provided in Section 6. A comparative study is provided in Section 7. A discussion on important remarks about ActiSiamese, its computational aspects, advantages and limitations is found in Section 8. We conclude in Section 9.

70 2. Preliminaries

Online learning considers a data generating process that provides at each time t a sequence of examples $S = \{S^t\}_{t=1}^T$, where $S^t = \{(x_i^t, y_i^t)\}_{i=1}^M$. The number of steps is denoted by $T \in [1, \infty)$ where the data are typically sampled from a long, potentially infinite, sequence. The number of examples at each 75 step is denoted by M . If $M = 1$, it is termed **one-by-one online** learning, otherwise it is termed **batch-by-batch online** learning [2]. The examples are drawn from an unknown probability distribution $p^t(x, y)$, where $x^t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is a d -dimensional vector in the input space $X \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, $y^t \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ is the class label in the target space $Y \subset \mathbb{Z}^+$, and $K \geq 2$ is the number of classes.

80 We focus on one-by-one learning, i.e., $S^t = (x^t, y^t)$, which is important for real-time monitoring. One-by-one learning requires the model to adapt imme-

¹<https://github.com/kmalialis/actisiamese>

diately upon seeing a new example, and algorithms intended for batch-by-batch learning are, typically, not applicable for one-by-one learning tasks [3]. A one-by-one online classifier receives a new instance x^t at time t and makes a prediction \hat{y}^t based on a concept $h : X \rightarrow Y$. In **online supervised** learning, the classifier receives the true label y^t , its performance is evaluated using a loss function and is then trained based on the loss incurred. This process is repeated at each step. The gradual adaptation of the classifier without complete re-training $h^t = h^{t-1}.train(\cdot)$ is termed **incremental** learning [12]. The rate or frequency of adaptation, and its associated costs and benefits, have been examined in [13].

In streaming tasks, however, the label cannot be typically provided, as it's either impossible (e.g. in real-time tasks) or costly / impractical. To address this issue, an alternative paradigm is **active** learning [6], which deals with strategies to selectively query for labels from a human expert according to a pre-defined "budget" $B \in [0, 1]$, e.g., $B = 0.2$ means that 20% of the arriving instances can be labelled. A budget spending mechanism must ensure that the labelling spending $b \in [0, 1]$ does not exceed the allocated budget.

In **online active** learning [14], a classifier is built that receives a new instance x^t at time t . At each time step the classifier calculates the prediction probability $\hat{p}(y|x^t)$. The classifier outputs the best prediction probability $h(x^t) = \max_y \hat{p}(y|x^t)$ and the predicted class $\hat{y}^t = \operatorname{argmax}_y \hat{p}(y|x^t)$. A given active learning strategy $\alpha : X \rightarrow \{False, True\}$ decides if the true label y^t is required, which is assumed that an expert will provide. The classifier is evaluated using a loss function and is then trained based on the loss incurred. Note that training occurs only if the budget allows and when $\alpha(x^t) = True$.

Since data are sampled from a long, potentially infinite, sequence which is typically the case in data streams, it is unrealistic to expect that all acquired labels will be available at all times. The classifier should use a fixed amount of memory for data storage. If learning occurs on the most recent example, without using a memory, it is termed **one-pass** learning [2]. In such case, the cost J at time t is calculated using the loss function l as follows $J = l(y^t, h(x^t))$.

A significant challenge encountered in some streaming applications is that

of data **nonstationarity** [2, 15, 16], typically caused by **concept drift**, which represents a change in the joint probability. The drift between steps t_i and t_j , where $i \neq j$, is defined as:

$$p^{t_i}(x, y) \neq p^{t_j}(x, y) \tag{1}$$

Another major challenge encountered in some streaming applications is the presence of infrequent events, also known as **class imbalance** [5]. It occurs when at least one class is under-represented, thus constituting a minority class. In binary classification, imbalance is defined as follows:

$$\exists y_0, y_1 \in Y \quad p^t(y = y_0) \gg p^t(y = y_1), \tag{2}$$

where y_1 represents the minority class.

3. Related Work

3.1. Online supervised learning

115 Methods that address drift fall into three groups. Memory-based methods use data storage (e.g., a sliding window) to maintain a set of recent examples that a classifier is trained on. Change detection-based methods use statistical tests to detect drift. Ensembling refers to a set of classifiers which can incorporate new concepts by adding new classifiers, and “forget” old concepts
 120 by discarding or updating existing ones [17]. We direct the interested reader towards these excellent surveys [2, 15, 18, 16, 19, 12, 20].

3.1.1. Class imbalance

The *combined* problem of class imbalance and concept drift remains an open challenge [21, 3]. There are two types of approaches, algorithm-level and data-
 125 level. Examples of algorithm-level methods include modified splitting criteria and distance metrics to make skew-insensitive the Decision Tree (e.g., [22]) and Nearest Neighbour (e.g., [23]) classifiers respectively. Genetic Programming has also been used, and this method [24] increases skew-insensitive rule

interpretability and recovery speed from drift. Cost-sensitive learning, one-class
130 classification, and anomaly detection are other types of methods that can handle imbalance. We direct the interested reader towards these excellent surveys [21, 3].

Examples of data-level approaches refer to resampling methods, which alter the training set to deal with the skewed distribution. In contrast to stationary
135 environments, resampling methods require dedicated strategies or mechanisms to handle imbalance in data streams. The idea of having separate memories and, specifically, queues for each class to address imbalance is introduced by Queue-Based Resampling [25]. Adaptive REBALancing (AREBA) [10] extends this idea and proposes a dynamic mechanism to adaptively modify the size of
140 the queues to constantly maintain separate and balanced queues per class. To address the problem of imbalance, resampling has been combined with ensemble learning, specifically, online bagging. Such examples, include, Oversampling-based Online Bagging (OOB) [26], Kappa Updated Ensemble (KUE) [27], and Robust Online Self-adjusting Ensemble (ROSE) [28]. Other ensemble methods,
145 include, EONN [29], ESOS-ELM [30], GRE [31] and HEEM [32].

While these algorithms have been shown to be effective, they typically rely on supervision [21, 3].

3.2. Online active learning

3.2.1. Querying strategies

The most common strategy is **uncertainty sampling**, where the learner queries the most uncertain instances, which are typically found near the decision boundary [33]. The majority of existing active learning strategies assume the availability of all training examples $U \subset X$ (offline active learning) [34]. One way to measure uncertainty [6] is to first find the instance x_q with the least confident best prediction:

$$x_q = \underset{x \in U}{\operatorname{argmin}} h(x) \quad (3)$$

where $h(x) = \max_y \hat{p}(y|x)$ and request its label if it satisfies:

$$h(x_q) < \theta, \tag{4}$$

150 where θ is a threshold which is typically fixed.

Some works consider batch-by-batch online active learning [35, 36, 37]. To address drift, [35] uses ensembling, [36] uses a sliding window approach, while [37] uses a change detection-based method. Work on one-by-one online active learning is limited. The arriving x^t is queried if:

$$h(x^t) < \theta, \tag{5}$$

where $h(x^t) = \max_y \hat{p}(y|x^t)$ and θ is a fixed threshold. This is called a *fixed uncertainty sampling* strategy [14].

This strategy may not perform well if the threshold is set incorrectly, or if the classifier learns enough so that the uncertainty remains above the fixed threshold most of the time. In [14] a variable uncertainty sampling strategy is proposed, which incorporates randomisation to ensure that the probability of labelling any instance is non-zero. This is called a *randomised variable uncertainty sampling (RVUS)* strategy and the threshold is modified as follows:

$$\theta = \begin{cases} \theta(1 - s) & \text{if } h(x^t) < \theta_{rdm} \text{ \# request label} \\ \theta(1 + s) & \text{if } h(x^t) \geq \theta_{rdm} \text{ \# don't request} \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

where s is a step size parameter, $\theta_{rdm} = \theta * \eta$ where η follows a Normal distribution $\eta \sim N(1, \delta)$ with a standard deviation of δ . Another work that proposes
155 a variable uncertainty sampling strategy is [38].

Query-by-committee [39] is a popular approach where a set of classifiers, referred to as the committee, is in place. Each committee member “votes” or predicts the label and the most informative query is considered to be the instance they disagree the most. The majority are offline active learning methods. Early
160 examples are *query by bagging* and *query by boosting* [40] while another one is *Active-DECORATE* [41], which focuses on building a diverse committee. An

abstaining mechanism is proposed in [42] to temporarily remove uncertain classifiers, with dynamically adjusting the abstaining criterion in favour of minority classes. In [43], the problem has been approached as a multi-armed bandit problem, which obtains an efficient and adaptive ensemble active learning procedure by selecting the most competent classifier from the pool for each query.

An alternative strategy is **density sampling**, whose idea is that informative instances are not only those which lie near the decision boundary, but also those which lie in high density regions i.e. those which inhabit dense regions of the input space according to a distance or similarity metric. As with uncertainty sampling, the majority of work is on offline active learning where the set of all unlabelled instances $U \subset X$ is already available. In [44] the instance queried for labelling is selected by its average similarity to other instances in U as follows:

$$\operatorname{argmax}_{x \in U} \frac{1}{|U|} \sum_{x_u \in U} \operatorname{sim}(x, x_u), \quad (7)$$

where $x \neq x_u$ and sim is a similarity function (e.g., cosine). This has also been applied in batch-by-batch online learning where an informative instance is the one which is similar to other unlabelled instances in the most recent batch [45].

Hybrid strategies have been proposed where various methods are combined to query even more informative instances. In [44], the authors combine offline density sampling with another strategy, such as, uncertainty sampling or query-by-committee. In [45], the authors use a batch-by-batch online active learning strategy where informative instances are selected based on uncertainty, density and overlap. A one-by-one online active learning strategy is proposed in [46] that uses uncertainty and density sampling.

An important and desirable property of online active learning strategies is their data processing functionality [47]. Ideally, one-pass (or single-pass) ensures that data is loaded sample-wise, the sample is processed through the active learning strategy, the classifier is updated if the strategy returned true, and then the sample is immediately discarded. Examples include the aforementioned [14, 38], as well as [48, 49]. When storage is used (e.g., window), it is essential that a fixed amount of memory is allowed for any storage [15].

Thus far, we have reviewed “classical” incremental approaches inspired by
 185 the machine learning and data mining community. An alternative line of re-
 search has focussed on enhanced evolving approaches (fuzzy models) inspired
 by the soft computing community, which can deal with significant novelty con-
 tent, and allows knowledge expansion of the models on-the-fly based on selected
 samples [47]. Representative works, include, [50], [51] and [52]. We direct the in-
 190 terested reader towards [47] for a comprehensive review of online active learning
 strategies, including, evolving (fuzzy) approaches.

For completeness, active learning has been combined with other learning
 paradigms, such as, semi-supervised and unsupervised learning [53, 54, 55].

One contribution of this work is that we propose a new density-based online
 195 active learning strategy, whose novel characteristic is that the similarity is con-
 sidered in the latent / encoding space rather than in the input / feature space.
 Also, no online active learning strategy addresses effectively the combination of
 drift and imbalance, while our work focuses exactly on this joint problem.

3.2.2. Budget spending mechanisms

200 One approach is to count the *exact* labelling spending [14]. Its drawback
 is that the contribution of every next label will diminish over infinite time.
 One way to solve the aforementioned problem is to count the *exact* labelling
 spending over a sliding window $b^t = \frac{u_w^t}{w}$, where u_w^t is the number of instances
 queried within the sliding window w . This, however, contradicts the incremental
 205 learning concept as it needs to record previously labelling decisions. The authors
 in [14] approximate the labelling spending $\hat{b}^t = \frac{\hat{u}_w^t}{w}$ by approximating the number
 of instances queried within the sliding window as follows: $\hat{u}_w^t = \lambda \hat{u}_w^{t-1} + a(x^t)$,
 where $\lambda = \frac{w-1}{w}$ and $a(x^t)$ is a Boolean value that indicates if the true label for
 x^t is queried or not. The authors prove that \hat{b} is an unbiased estimate of b .

210 4. Proposed Method

ActiSiamese’s overview is shown in Fig 1. The component Q^t is a multi-
 queue memory where each class has its own sliding window which is implemented

Figure 1: ActiSiamese’s architecture which synergistically combines a multi-queue memory (left), a classifier or an ensemble of classifiers (middle), and online active learning (right).

as a queue. In essence, this is ActiSiamese’s way to deal with concept drift. The middle component denotes the classifier; notice that ensembling is supported.

215 The component on the right depicts the active learning strategy. Specifically, at any time t , we observe an arriving instance x^t . The classifier considers the examples in Q^t , and provides the predicted class \hat{y}^t . The flow of information for the prediction part is shown in yellow. If the active learning strategy requests the label, this is provided by the oracle. Alternatively, nothing is done and the

220 algorithm waits for the next arriving instance. This is shown in green. The flow of information for incrementally training the classifier is shown in orange. Each component is described below in detail. Towards the end of this section, we discuss our design choices, computational aspects, and other important remarks.

4.1. Multi-queue memory

The framework uses multiple first-in-first-out (FIFO) queues that will be populated by examples queried by the active learning strategy. At any time t we maintain a set of K queues, one for each class as follows:

$$Q^t = \{q_c^t\}_{c=1}^K, \quad (8)$$

where c is a class and $K \geq 2$ is the number of classes. All queues are of the same capacity L and a queue corresponding to class c is defined as follows:

$$q_c^t = \{x_{c,i}\}_{i=1}^L, \quad (9)$$

225 where for any two $x_{c,i}, x_{c,j} \in q_c^t$ such that $j > i$, $x_{c,j}$ has been observed more recently in time.

ActiSiamese assumes that the queues are initially full, i.e., it assumes the initial availability of L labelled examples per class. While this may be difficult to have in practise, we will show that ActiSiamese is effective for very small
230 values of L , e.g., up to ten. We argue that for the vast majority of applications this assumption is realistic. The assumption is not needed for problems in which imbalance does not exist, as the queues will be populated at a similar rate.

4.2. ActiSiamese

While the proposed architecture doesn't impose any restrictions on the selection of the classifier, we propose the use of Siamese neural networks which have
235 been demonstrated (in the offline supervised learning framework) to be capable of few-shot learning, that is, learning from a few examples per class [56].

At the core of ActiSiamese lies a siamese neural network [57] that consists of two identical neural networks (the "twins") as depicted in Fig 2. The basic
240 idea is to learn a function e that maps an input pattern x into a *latent* space, thus forming its "encoding" $e(x)$, in such a way that a simple distance in the latent space approximates the neighbourhood relationships in the input space.

Traditional models, e.g. the *k-nearest neighbour (k-NN)* algorithm, consider neighbourhood distances in the *input* space and, it is for this reason
245 that siamese networks have significantly outperformed these models in high-dimensional spaces, e.g., for image recognition [56].

Given a pair of examples (x_i, x_j) , the distance metric used is the element-wise absolute difference as in [58]:

$$d(x_i, x_j) = |e(x_i) - e(x_j)| \quad (10)$$

Figure 2: A siamese neural network.

The calculated distance is then provided to a sigmoid output unit. The siamese network $\hat{p} : X \times X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ will learn to output a probability $\hat{p}(x_i, x_j)$ that indicates if the elements of the pair (x_i, x_j) belongs to the same class.

Class prediction: To predict the class of the arriving x^t (yellow part in Fig. 1), ActiSiamese considers all examples in Q^t . For each queue, we find the average similarity of x^t to its elements. We choose the queue with the highest average similarity:

$$\hat{y}^t = \operatorname{argmax}_{c \in \{1, \dots, K\}} \frac{1}{L} \sum_{i=1}^L \hat{p}(x^t, x_{c,i}), \quad (11)$$

250 where K is the number of classes, and $x_{c,i} \in q_c^t$.

Active learning strategy: This work focuses on one-by-one learning strategies (green part in Fig. 1). ActiSiamese proposes a randomised variable *similarity* sampling (RVSS) strategy, where the selection criterion value is the maximum similarity in the predicted class:

$$v = \max_{i \in \{1, \dots, L\}} \hat{p}(x^t, x_{c,i}), \quad (12)$$

where c is the class selected using Eq. (11). This criterion is compared to a variable threshold to determine whether or not to trigger selection, as follows:

$$\theta = \begin{cases} \theta(1 - s) & \text{if } v < \theta_{rdm} \text{ \# request label} \\ \theta(1 + s) & \text{if } v \geq \theta_{rdm} \text{ \# don't request} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where s is a step size parameter, $\theta_{rdm} = \theta * \eta$ where η follows a Normal distribution $\eta \sim N(1, \delta)$ with a standard deviation of δ . This was inspired by RVUS

[14] as shown in Eq. (6), although, the selection criterion value is no longer $h(x^t) = \max_y \hat{p}(y|x^t)$, but instead it is the proposed v .

255 Notice that ActiSiamese uses a *one-by-one* online active learning strategy. In other words, when the active learning strategy returns true, it requests the label of only the most recently observed instance x^t . Therefore, the proposed method does not need or store past unlabelled data. Recall that the memory (multi-queue) holds only some of the previously labelled data.

260 Lastly, we use the budget spending mechanism from [14] described in Section 3.2.2, however, any mechanism can be used which ensures that the labelling spending b does not exceed the allocated budget B .

Incremental training: Recall that training (orange part in Fig. 1) is initiated only when the active learning strategy requests and receives a class label. At time t , we generate from Q^t all possible combinations of size two C_2^t . We then generate two subsets of C_2^t as described below. The first subset contains all pairs in which the two examples belong to the same class, while the second subset contains all pairs in which the two examples belong to different queues:

$$Q_{pos}^t = \{\forall (x_{c_1, i_1}, x_{c_2, i_2}) \in C_2^t | c_1 = c_2\} \quad (14)$$

$$Q_{neg}^t = \{\forall (x_{c_1, i_1}, x_{c_2, i_2}) \in C_2^t | c_1 \neq c_2\} \quad (15)$$

Importantly, we ensure that the two sets are always balanced and, if necessary, we perform random downsampling to Q_{neg}^t . The training set is thus formed as follows:

$$Q_{train}^t = Q_{pos}^t \cup Q_{neg}^t \quad (16)$$

Let $t - \Delta$ be the time of the last training, i.e., the last time a class label was requested and provided by an expert. Let also t be the current time, and let's assume that the active learning strategy requested and received the class label. The cost function J^t at time t is defined as follows:

$$J^t = \frac{1}{|Q_{train}^t|} \sum_{(x_i, x_j) \in Q_{train}^t} l(y_{i,j}, \hat{p}(x_i, x_j)) \quad (17)$$

where $y_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}$ is the ground truth and the loss function l used is the binary

cross-entropy. Learning is performed using incremental stochastic gradient de-
 265 scendent where each neural network weight w is updated according to the formula
 $w^t \leftarrow w^{t-\Delta} - \alpha \frac{\partial J^t}{w}$, where $\frac{\partial J^t}{w}$ is the partial derivative with respect to w , and α
 is the learning rate. ActiSiamese is trained using the backpropagation algorithm
 [59]. We clarify that ActiSiamese’s architecture remains fixed, and no layers are
 incrementally added; there is no evolution of any structural components.

270 ActiSiamese’s pseudocode is shown in Algorithm 1.

4.3. ActiSiamese-WM

This algorithm refers to a collection of N classifiers $\{S_i\}_{i=1}^N$, where S_i is an
 ActiSiamese classifier.

Class prediction: In this work, we consider the popular *Weighted Majority*
 (WM) algorithm [60]. We maintain a pool of weights for each classifier: $\{w_i\}_{i=1}^N$.
 For each arriving instance x^t , each classifier provides a prediction probability
 $\hat{p}(c|x^t)$ for each class $c \in \{1, \dots, K\}$. We then calculate the weighted average
 probability for each class:

$$\{\hat{p}_{avg}^t(c|x^t)\}_{c=1}^K \quad (18)$$

The algorithm predicts the class of each x^t as follows:

$$\hat{y}^t = \operatorname{argmax}_c \hat{p}_{avg}^t(c|x^t) \quad (19)$$

The weight of each classifier i is updated using the formula below:

$$w_i^t \leftarrow w_i^{t-1} e^{-\beta z_i^t}, \quad (20)$$

where z_i^t is the zero-one (0/1) loss of classifier i at time t and β is a pre-specified
 275 multiplicative factor [60].

Active learning strategy: We use the proposed randomised variable *simi-*
larity sampling strategy described in the previous section, however, the selection
 criterion value is now given as follows:

$$v = \max_{c \in \{1, \dots, K\}} \hat{p}_{avg}^t(c|x^t) \quad (21)$$

Incremental training: Each Siamese network S_i is trained exactly as de-
 scribed earlier in Eq. (17).

Algorithm 1 ActiSiamese

Input:

- 1: a : active learning strategy
- 2: B : labelling budget
- 3: K : number of classes
- 4: L : queue length
- 5: D : labelled data ▷ Optional, $|D| = K \times L$

Initialisation:

- 6: init queues $Q^0 = FIFO(num = K, capacity = L, init = D)$
- 7: init budget expenses $b^0 = 0$
- 8: create model h^0

Main:

- 9: **for** each time step $t \in [1, \infty)$ **do**
 - 10: receive instance $x^t \in \mathbb{R}^d$
 - 11: predict class \hat{y}^t using Eq. (11)
 - 12: $Q^t = Q^{t-1}$
 - 13: $h^t = h^{t-1}$
 - 14: **if** $b^{t-1} < B$ **then** ▷ expenses within budget
 - 15: calculate query criterion value v using Eq. (12)
 - 16: **if** $a(x^t, v) == True$ **then** ▷ label request using Eq. 13
 - 17: receive true label y^t
 - 18: append example $Q^t = Q^{t-1}.append(x^t, y^t)$
 - 19: prepare training pairs Q_{train}^t using Eq. (16)
 - 20: calculate cost J^t using Eq. (17)
 - 21: update classifier $h^t = h^{t-1}.train(J^t)$
 - 22: update budget expenses b^t ▷ Section 3.2.2
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5. Experimental Setup

5.1. Datasets

280 5.1.1. Synthetic datasets

These are necessary as they provide us with the flexibility to control the simulation conditions i.e. the imbalance rate, when to introduce drift, and the nature of the drift.

Figure 3: The synthetic data used in our experimental study.

sea [61]: It consists of two features $x_1, x_2 \in [0, 15]$. The original dataset was a binary classification problem; we have extended it here to ten classes. The

decision boundaries are shown in Fig. 3a and defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \rho_0 \leq x_1 + x_2 < \rho_1 &\rightarrow \text{class 1 (pink)} \\
 \rho_1 \leq x_1 + x_2 < \rho_2 &\rightarrow \text{class 2 (brown)} \\
 &\dots \\
 \rho_9 \leq x_1 + x_2 < \rho_{10} &\rightarrow \text{class 10 (red)}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{22}$$

The parameter values are $\rho = \langle 0, 2, 4, \dots, 18, 30 \rangle$. We will consider a version
 285 of this dataset with posterior concept drift as depicted in Fig. 3b, where the
 parameters become $\rho = \langle 0, 12, 14, \dots, 30 \rangle$. We will consider cases where the
 drift occurs abruptly and recurrently. Furthermore, we will consider a version
 of *sea* with prior drift, where initially the probability of all classes is $p(y) = 0.1$.
 After a specified time, this will change to a multi-minority imbalance scenario.

290 **circles** [62]: It consists of two features $x_1, x_2 \in [0, 15]$ and ten classes as
 shown in Fig. 3c. Each class is represented by a circle of the form $(x_1 - x_{1c})^2 +$
 $(x_2 - x_{2c})^2 = r_c^2$ where (x_{1c}, x_{2c}) and r_c are its centre and radius respectively.
 Like with the *sea* dataset, we will consider posterior (depicted in Fig. 3d) and
 prior types of drift, as well as abrupt and recurrent drift.

295 **blobs**: It consists of three features $x_1, x_2, x_3 \in [0, 15]$ and 12 classes as
 shown in Fig. 3e. Each class is an isotropic Gaussian blob and noise exists due
 to the standard deviation of the blobs. As before, we will consider abrupt and
 recurrent posterior concept drift as depicted in Fig. 3f.

Notice that these datasets exhibit a different level of posterior drift severity,
 300 specifically, drift is mild, severe and extreme in the *circles*, *blobs* and *sea* data
 respectively. Moreover, we will consider abrupt and recurrent types of drift.

Furthermore, we produce imbalanced versions of the above datasets. We
 consider the more challenging multi-minority class imbalance scenarios [63]. We
 have chosen the pink class to be the majority class, and the rest constitute
 305 minority classes with the same imbalance rate. We consider cases of severe
 (1%) and extreme (0.1%) imbalance. For example, for *sea* where the number
 of classes is $K = 10$, the extreme multi-minority scenario would correspond to:
 $p(y = \text{pink}) = 1.0 - (K - 1) \times p(y \in \text{minority}) = 1.0 - 9 \times 0.001 = 0.991$.

Two Patterns [64]: A simulated time series dataset in which each class
310 represents the presence of two step patterns (up, down). There are 128 features,
5000 examples, 4 classes (down-down, up-down, down-up, up-up), and it is a
balanced dataset.

Moving Squares [65]: Four equidistantly separated, squared uniform dis-
tributions are moving in horizontal direction with constant speed. The direction
315 is inverted whenever the leading square reaches a predefined boundary. Each
square represents a different class. There is a predefined time horizon of 120
examples before old instances may start to overlap current ones.

Interchanging RBF [65]: Fifteen Gaussians with random covariance ma-
trices are replacing each other every 3000 samples. Thereby, the number of
320 Gaussians switching their position increases each time by one until all are si-
multaneously changing their location. Altogether 67 abrupt drifts are occurring
within this dataset.

5.1.2. Real-world datasets

These are high-dimensional, noisy, and more challenging than synthetic
325 datasets, however, the true nature of concept drift may be unknown.

gestures [66]: The task is to classify four human gestures from electrical
activity of muscles (electromyography). Eight sensors are placed on skin surface,
and each arriving instance includes eight consecutive readings i.e. 64 features.
This dataset is balanced as the number of arriving instances per class is 2500.

330 **Forest** [67]: It contains cartographic information from the U.S. Forest Ser-
vice. The task is to predict the forest cover type for given 30x30m cells from
the Roosevelt National Forest in Colorado. There are seven forest cover types
each with 20000, 30000, 3500, 275, 1000, 1500, 2000 instances respectively.

MNIST [68]: The dataset consists of handwritten digits (“0”-“9”) where
335 each image is of size 28x28. While it is, typically used as a benchmark for
training image classification systems, we use it in our study as it can stress test
streaming algorithms with its high dimensionality of 784 features. We consider
two multi-minority scenarios where the majority class is the digit “0” and the

rest of the digits are the minority classes. In the first scenario the imbalance
340 level is 10%, that is, 5000 arriving images of digit “0”, and 500 from each of the
remaining digits. In the second scenario the imbalance level is 1%, that is, 5000
arriving images of digit “0”, and 50 from each of the remaining digits.

Keystroke [69]: The dataset was constructed after 51 users were requested
to type a specific password which was captured in eight sessions over different
345 days. The task is to identify four different users based on their typing rhythm.
It has 1600 examples and ten features which are extracted from the “flight time”
for each pressed key; defined as the difference between the times when a key is
released and when the next one is pressed.

UWave Gesture Library Z [70]: A time series dataset for a set of eight
350 simple gestures generated from accelerometers using the Wii remote. The data
consists of the Z coordinates of each motion. There are 8 classes with total 3582
samples with 315 features.

Insects [71]: These are data generated by a low-cost laser sensor, where the
task is to classify species of insects. This task is important as it constitutes a
355 step towards the development of intelligent traps, which will be able to capture
species of interest (e.g., for pest control, during diseases). The data stream is
nonstationary as the insects’ metabolisms are influenced by environmental con-
ditions (e.g. temperature), circadian rhythm, and age. The number of features
are 33 and the imbalance ratio is 20%.

360 5.2. Compared methods

RVUS: The seminal work [14] described in Sec. 3.2.1 and shown in Eq. (6).
It uses an uncertainty-based active learning strategy, a standard neural network,
and it is a one-pass learner (no memory).

RVUS-WM: The ensemble version of RVUS with size is $N = 10$ and the
365 multiplicative factor of the Weighted Majority algorithm is set to $\beta = 0.5$.

ActiQ: A state-of-the-art uncertainty-based algorithm [11] which uses the
RVUS, but within the proposed architecture shown in Fig. 1. In other words,

similarly to RVUS it uses a standard neural network, and similarly to ActiSiamese it uses the multi-queue memory.

370 **ActiQ-WM:** The ensemble version of ActiQ.

RVSS: A randomised variable similarity sampling active learning strategy using cosine similarity as in [6]. It uses the memory (multi-queue) from the proposed architecture (Fig. 1). Similarity is considered in the input space (rather than the latent space).

375 **RVSS-WM:** The ensemble version of RVSS.

ActiSiamese: The proposed method described in Section 4.2 and Algorithm 1. It uses a similarity-based active learning strategy, a Siamese network, and it is a memory-based method. Similarity is considered in the latent space.

ActiSiamese-WM: The ensemble version of ActiSiamese (Section 4.3).

380 Our comparative study examines many crucial aspects of learning in data streams, which are: i) one-pass learning (RVUS) vs memory-based (RVSS, ActiQ, ActiSiamese); ii) uncertainty-based (RVUS, ActiQ) vs similarity-based (RVSS, ActiSiamese) sampling strategies; iii) similarity-based in the input space (RVSS) vs the latent space (ActiSiamese); and iv) single classifier (RVUS, 385 RVSS, ActiQ, ActiSiamese) vs ensembling (RVUS-WM, RVSS-WM, ActiQ-WM, ActiSiamese-WM).

We have tried to make the comparison as fair as possible. First, we ensure that no *offline* learning, i.e., no pre-training takes place. This means that *all* methods start learning online at time $t = 1$ even if ActiQ and ActiSiamese have 390 access to E initial examples per class. Second, all active learning strategies use the same parameter values, as suggested by [14]: step size $s = 0.01$, randomisation threshold $\delta = 1.0$ and sliding window size $w = 300$. Third, all methods share the same classifier per dataset, which is standard neural network. For ActiSiamese, it is replicated to form the “twin network”.

395 Classifiers are implemented in Keras [72]. For reproducibility, the hyperparameter values for synthetic datasets are shown in Table 1. The hyperparameter values for real-world datasets are shown in Table 2; any values not shown are the same as in the synthetic datasets. Notice that the output acti-

Table 1: Hyper-parameter values for synthetic data

	Sea	Circles	Blobs	Two Patterns	Interchanging RBF	Moving Squares
Learning rate	0.01			0.001		
Hidden layers	[32, 32]		[256, 256]	[64, 64]	[8, 32]	
Mini-batch size	64			128		
Weight initialiser	He Normal [73]					
Optimiser	Adam [74]					
Hidden activation	Leaky ReLU($\lambda = 0.01$) [75]					
Num. of epochs	1					
Output activation	Binary (ActiSiamese) / Categorical cross-entropy					
Loss function	Sigmoid (ActiSiamese) / Softmax					

Table 2: Hyper-parameter values for real-world data

	Gestures	Insects	Forest	Keystroke	UWave Gestures	MNIST
Learning rate	0.001					0.0001
Hidden layers	[128, 128]	[32, 32]	[64, 128]	[512, 1024]	[1024, 1024]	
Mini-batch size	128					

400 vation and loss function depend on the type of the neural network used. The standard fully-connected network learns the probability of an arriving example x^t belonging to each class, i.e., $\hat{p}(y|x^t)$. As a result, the categorical cross-entropy loss function and the softmax output activation are used. In contrast, the Siamese network learns to output a probability $\hat{p}(x_i, x_j)$ that indicates if the elements of the pair of examples (x_i, x_j) belongs to the same class (Fig. 2). As
 405 a result, the binary cross-entropy and the sigmoid output activation are used.

5.3. Performance metrics and Evaluation method

Classifiers are typically evaluated using the overall accuracy metric. In the presence of imbalance, however, this metric becomes unsuitable as it is biased towards the majority class(es) [5]. A widely accepted performance metric which is not sensitive to imbalance is the geometric mean: [76]:

$$G\text{-mean} = \sqrt[\kappa]{\prod_{c=1}^K R_c}, \quad (23)$$

where R_c is the recall of class c and K is the number of classes. Not only $G\text{-mean}$ is not sensitive to imbalance, it has some desirable properties as it is

high when all recalls are high and when their difference is small [5].

410 To evaluate and compare sequential learning algorithms, we use the popular *prequential evaluation with fading factors* method. It has been proven to converge to the Bayes error when learning in stationary data [77]. Moreover, a major advantage is that it does not require a holdout set and the predictive algorithm is always tested on unseen data. The fading factor is set to $\xi = 0.99$.
415 In all simulations we plot the prequential *G-mean* in every step averaged over 20 repetitions, including the error bars displaying the standard error around the mean. In some plots the error bars are very small but they are always included.

Moreover, we test for statistical significance using a one-way repeated measures ANOVA and then using posthoc multiple comparisons tests with Fisher’s
420 least significant difference correction procedure to show which of the compared method is significantly different from the others.

6. Empirical Analysis of ActiSiamese

6.1. Effect of the budget B

Stationary data: Figs 4a - 4c depict the results for the three synthetic
425 datasets under stationary conditions. The “SL” corresponds to online supervised learning i.e. the label is presented at each step. Simulations were performed for 20000 steps, therefore, the final performance is measured at $t = 20000$. The queue capacity is set to $L = 10$. RVUS performs significantly worse than the proposed ActiQ and ActiSiamese. The ActiQ and ActiSiamese obtain
430 overall a similar final performance. Specifically, in Fig 4a and 4b ActiQ performs slightly better, while in Fig 4c ActiSiamese performs slightly better. In a later section, however, we will show that their learning speed differs substantially.

Nonstationary data: For *sea*, the same experiment was repeated when drift occurs abruptly at $t = 5000$. We measure the performance at $t = 5500$, i.e.
435 only 500 steps after the drift, to examine the short-term effect of the drift on performance. This is depicted in Fig 4d. The performance of RVUS declines as the budget gets smaller, however, the decline rate is worse compared to Fig 4a.

Figure 4: The effect of the budget B on the performance ($t = 20000$) under balanced data.

Furthermore, we observe a significant drop in performance for ActiQ when the budget is $B = 1\%$. The performance at $t = 20000$, that is, 15000 steps after the drift, is shown in Fig 4e. It is almost identical to Fig 4a, i.e., all algorithms have recovered from the drift. In summary, important remarks are as follows:

- RVUS' final performance severely declines as the budget gets smaller.
- For ActiQ and ActiSiamese, the decline rate is very small, even negligible in some cases, with the exception of ActiQ when $B = 1\%$ under drift. These approaches are robust to the choice of the budget.
- We have the first evidence that the multi-queue memory is beneficial compared to the one-pass learner RVUS.

Figure 5: The effect of L on ActiSiamese under severe (1%) imbalance.

6.2. Role of the queue capacity L

Stationary data: Figs 5a - 5b show the learning curves for ActiSiamese in *sea* and *circles* respectively. The curves show the prequential G-mean at every step. For all experiments the budget is $B = 1\%$ and imbalance is severe (1%). We conclude that the higher the value of L the higher the performance, however, diminishing returns are obtained, e.g., the cases where $L = 50$ and $L = 100$ do not differ considerably. Importantly, irrespective of the value of L , ActiSiamese learns fast (all learning curves are steep). This is in contrast to ActiQ shown in Figs 6a - 6b where the choice of L significantly affects its learning speed.

Nonstationary data: Figs 5c - 5d show the learning curves for ActiSiamese in *sea* and *circles* respectively where drift occurs abruptly at $t = 5000$. Hence, let's focus on the part of the curves after the drift i.e. $t \geq 5000$. In Fig 5c where

Figure 6: The effect of L on ActiQ under severe (1%) imbalance.

460 the drift is more severe, we observe a variation in performance (indicated by
the shaded regions) and a slight decrease in the final performance compared to
Fig 5a. ActiSiamese is robust to the choice of L ; for comparison, Figs 6c - 6d
show the analogous plots for ActiQ. To sum up, important remarks are:

- 465 • In stationary data, ActiSiamese with larger values of L performs better,
however, diminishing returns are obtained.
- In nonstationary data, ActiSiamese is still robust to the choice of L , how-
ever, a slight performance variation is observed after the drift.
- We have the first evidence that the use of a Siamese network is beneficial
compared to ActiQ, which uses a standard neural network.

Figure 7: Comparative study in sea: (a) normal (balanced, stationary), (b) extreme (0.1%) imbalance, (c) abrupt drift, (d) extreme imbalance and abrupt drift, and (e) recurrent drift.

470 7. Comparative Study

7.1. Synthetic datasets

Figs. 7a-7e show the performance of the methods in the sea dataset under normal conditions (stationary, balanced), extreme (0.1%) imbalance, abrupt drift, both extreme imbalance with abrupt drift, and recurrent drift respectively. In all experiments, the memory size is $L = 10$, and the budget is $B = 1\%$ unless otherwise stated.

In Fig. 7a, ActiSiamese learns significantly faster. Given more time, ActiQ will catch up. In Fig. 7b, the superiority of ActiSiamese is shown. In Fig. 7c both ActiSiamese and ActiQ (to a lesser degree) deal well with abrupt drift; notice how similar this figure with Fig. 7a is. The combination of drift with imbalance in Fig. 7d causes some variation in the performance throughout the

Figure 8: Comparative study in circles: (a) normal (balanced, stationary), (b) extreme (0.1%) imbalance, (c) abrupt drift, (d) extreme imbalance and abrupt drift, and (e) recurrent drift.

experiment’s duration. We have run another simulation experiment with recurrent drift shown in Fig. 7e. Given the challenging conditions of recurrent drift, the active learning budget has been increased from $B = 1\%$ to $B = 5\%$.

485 The analogous plots for circles and blobs are shown in Figs. 8a-8e and Figs. 9a-9e. The budget is set to $B = 1\%$ in all cases, except for recurrent drift in *blobs* which is $B = 5\%$ (Fig. 9e). Overall, similar results are observed. A notable observation is that in Fig. 8a, given additional time, ActiQ slightly outperforms ActiSiamese.

490 The results for the remaining of the synthetic datasets are depicted in Figs. 10a-10e. The active learning is $B = 10\%$ for circles, sea and Two Patterns, while for the more challenging Interchanging RBF and Moving Squares datasets it is set to $B = 30\%$. In Figs.10a and 10b, ActiSiamese has a superior learning speed; given additional time RVSS and ActiQ equalise its performance in sea

Figure 9: Comparative study in blobs: (a) normal (balanced, stationary), (b) extreme (0.1%) imbalance, (c) abrupt drift, (d) extreme imbalance and abrupt drift, and (e) recurrent drift.

495 and slightly outperform it in circles. In Figs. 10c and 10d ActiSiamese outperforms the rest. The “oscillations” observed in Fig. 10d are due to interchanging nature of drift. Interestingly, in Fig. 10e, RVSS outperforms the rest.

Taking everything into account, important remarks are as follows:

- ActiSiamese, ActiQ, and RVSS that use the multi-queue memory significantly outperform the one-pass learner RVUS in all scenarios.
- Among the memory-based methods, ActiSiamese learns significantly faster than the rest. Given more time, ActiQ and RVSS may equalise ActiSiamese or may even slightly outperform it.
- ActiSiamese is superior under class imbalance.
- The methods that use the multi-queue memory deal with drift well, and they are robust to it. However, under challenging drift conditions, we had

Figure 10: Comparative study for the rest of the synthetic datasets.

to increase the memory size and / or active learning budget.

- ActiSiamese, which considers similarity in the latent space significantly outperforms RVSS which considers similarity in the input space. An exception was observed in Fig. 10e.
- Overall, ensembles gain a few percentages of performance for all methods.

510

7.2. Real datasets

This section describes our study in real-world datasets. Figs. 11a - 11f show the performance of each method in the Gestures, MNIST, Forest, Keystroke, UWave Gestures, and Insects dataset respectively.

515

Recall that the active learning budget is critical to the success of a real-world application. A budget too large would correspond to too frequent interactions with a human expert, i.e., requesting ground truth information too often which

Figure 11: Comparative study for the real-world datasets.

could potentially cause a method to be impractical. It is for this reason, we
 520 have kept the budget to a low value; in Gestures, MNIST, and Forest (Figs. 11a
 - 11c) the budget is $B = 1\%$, while in Keystroke, UWave Gestures, and Insects
 (Figs. 11d - 11f) it is $B = 10\%$. The memory size is $L = 10$ for MNIST and
 Insects, and $L = 50$ for the rest which have proven to be more challenging due
 to the small budget.

525 In summary, the results are in alignment with those obtained in the synthetic
 datasets:

- The proposed methods (ActiSiamese, ActiSiamese-WM) significantly outperform the rest in two datasets (Gestures, Keystroke).
- ActiSiamese and ActiSiamese-WM learn significantly faster in two datasets
 530 (MNIST, Forest). In these two datasets, the final performance is similar

Table 3: Mean performance and standard deviation at the last time step (Gestures, UWave Gestures, Insects), and early in the learning process at $t = 500$ (MNIST, Forest, Keystroke).

	Gestures	MNIST	Forest	Keystroke	UWave Gestures	Insects
ActiSiamese (WM)	0.5616 (0.0189)	0.6785 (0.0238)	0.4654 (0.0571)	0.9428 (0.0041)	0.5778 (0.0175)	0.5263 (0.0208)
ActiSiamese	0.5456 (0.0191)	0.6193 (0.0376)	0.3653 (0.1857)	0.9393 (0.0061)	0.5729 (0.0180)	0.5258 (0.0179)
ActiQ (WM)	0.4311 (0.0239)	0.4415 (0.1563)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.8627 (0.0091)	0.6440 (0.0139)	0.5247 (0.0185)
ActiQ	0.4175 (0.0191)	0.4172 (0.0518)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.8322 (0.0212)	0.6441 (0.0097)	0.5269 (0.0168)
RVSS (WM)	0.4446 (0.0172)	0.4826 (0.0533)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.8634 (0.0115)	0.6442 (0.0095)	0.5293 (0.0167)
RVSS	0.4193 (0.0284)	0.4289 (0.0414)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.8396 (0.0253)	0.6463 (0.0116)	0.5259 (0.0159)
RVUS (WM)	0.2937 (0.0296)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.3340 (0.1957)	0.4770 (0.0212)	0.1456 (0.0804)
RVUS	0.2831 (0.0220)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.1761 (0.1605)	0.4739 (0.0209)	0.1548 (0.0794)

to RVSS(-WM) and ActiQ(-WM) which they make use of the multi-queue memory of the proposed methods.

- An exception where ActiSiamese performs worse is in the UWave Gestures. Expectedly, the proposed method is not the silver bullet to all problems.
- 535 • The one-pass learner RVUS (no memory) is significantly worse than the rest, except in Forest which obtains a similar performance to them.
- Ensemble learning gains a few percentages of performance for all methods.
- In challenging problems, larger values of the memory L and budget B , typically, improve the performance of all methods.

540 To verify the above, we further conducted a statistical analysis. The final performance (i.e., at the last time step) is examined for Gestures, UWave Gestures, and Insects, while the learning speed is examined early in the learning process ($t = 500$) for MNIST, Forest, and Keystroke. Table 7.2 shows the mean performances and standard deviations. The method which yields the higher
545 performance based on ANOVA and its posthoc tests (Section 5.3) is shown in bold font which denotes statistical significance over the others.

8. Discussion

In this section we discuss important remarks concerning ActiSiamese’s computational aspects, advantages, and limitations.

550 *8.1. Computational aspects*

Memory requirements: The memory size is $|Q^t| = K \times L$, and while the number of classes K depends on the problem, this work has demonstrated that ActiSiamese is effective when the queue capacity L is, typically, small (e.g., ten). Due to the pair creation process (discussed in the point below),
555 ActiSiamese makes use of $|Q_{train}^t|$ training data which is, typically, larger than $|Q^t|$. Importantly, ActiSiamese satisfies one of the most important and desired properties of learning in nonstationary environments, which is having a fixed amount of memory for any storage [15]. Ideally, however, an algorithm should be capable of one-pass learning; we discuss this below.

Training stage: A computational step of ActiSiamese is the creation of
560 pairs Q_{train}^t from the original examples Q^t . First, we have showed that ActiSiamese is effective even when the budget is low, hence, the pair creation process, which is initiated only during training, doesn't occur frequently. Second, only a fraction of the training pairs need to be re-calculated at each training step.
565 Third, ActiSiamese is updated once ($num_epochs = 1$) whenever trained. Not only this helps to reduce the training cost, it can also prevent overfitting.

Prediction stage: For prediction, ActiSiamese computes the average similarity of x^t to its elements as shown in Eq. (11). Significant computation speed can be gained by pre-computing the encodings, therefore, avoiding multiple and repeated forward propagation computations. For the ensemble version
570 ActiSiamese-WM, significant gains can be achieved using parallelisation.

8.2. Advantages

Class imbalance: ActiSiamese has three “embedded” mechanisms which make it robust to imbalance. First, the use of *separate* and *balanced* queues
575 per class alleviates the problem as propagating old examples in the most recent training set is a form of oversampling. Second, the data preparation step creates $|Q_{train}^t|$ training pairs from the $K \times L$ examples found in the original Q^t . The number of generated pairs depends on the values of K and L , however, most of the times it is expected that $|Q_{train}^t|$ will be considerably larger than $|Q^t|$,

580 thus constituting another form of oversampling. Third, the number of positive and negative pairs is always balanced. As a result, we will later show that ActiSiamese achieves a superior performance even under extreme imbalance.

Concept drift: ActiSiamese also has three mechanisms which make it robust to drift. First, it uses incremental learning to continually update the model
585 to reflect new changes as environments evolve. We have chosen this for a few reasons. Drift is a multifaceted problem which can be classified according to type, severity, speed, predictability, frequency, and recurrence [78]. As a result, it is hard to characterise and explicitly detect it in practise. Furthermore, there is no explicit drift detection mechanism that can perform well under any
590 combination of drift characteristics [79]. Therefore, we have decided to *learn* the concept drift using incremental training, rather than performing a complete re-training when drift is detected. We discuss this further in our future work section. Second, ActiSiamese uses a multi-queue memory. The fact that examples are carried over a series of steps allows the classifier to “remember” old concepts.
595 “Forgetting” old concepts is achieved when obsolete examples eventually drop off the queues. ActiSiamese is effective with small queue sizes, therefore, it ensures that obsolete examples will be discarded quicker. Third, ActiSiamese-WM which uses ensembling helps by de-prioritising obsolete classifiers.

8.3. Limitations

600 **Ome-pass learning:** In our diverse study, ActiSiamese has been shown to significantly outperform strong baseline and state-of-the-art methods under various conditions. We attribute this to the many characteristics of ActiSiamese which have been combined in a seamless and effective manner. These include, few-shot learning for performing similarity learning, incremental learning, and
605 the various mechanisms to handle imbalance and drift as discussed in Section 8.2.

This is, however, at the expense of ActiSiamese not being a one-pass learner. That is, if learning occurs using the most recently queried example, and then discarding it (i.e., without storing it in a memory), it is termed one-pass learning. Having said this, ActiSiamese satisfies one of the most important and desired

610 properties of learning in data streams, which is having a fixed amount of memory
for any storage. Also, ActiSiamese has been shown to be effective when the
queue capacity L is, typically, small (e.g., in the order of ten). These are
discussed in Section 8.1.

9. Conclusion

615 We proposed ActiSiamese which synergistically merges online active learn-
ing, a multi-queue memory, and siamese networks. It proposes a new density-
based active learning strategy which considers similarity in the latent space
rather than the input space. We conducted an extensive study where we show
that ActiSiamese outperforms baseline and state-of-the-art algorithms, and is
620 effective even under extreme imbalance, and even when only a fraction of the
arriving instances' labels is available. Future work will examine the following:

Semi-supervised learning: A limitation of active learning is that it solely
attempts to explore the search space by querying selected instances for their
class labels. In other words, it ignores all the arriving instances for which their
625 label is not requested. In contrast, semi-supervised learning assumes the initial
availability of labelled data which the classifier is trained with, but it later uses
its learnt knowledge to automatically classify the arriving instances [80]. Future
work will consider combining ActiSiamese with semi-supervised learning.

Explicit concept drift detection: ActiSiamese has an implicit way of
630 dealing with drift using incremental learning and a multi-queue memory. An
explicit drift detection mechanism (e.g., using statistical tests) could allow better
reaction to drift. Future work will consider incorporating such a mechanism.

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